

FACTORS AFFECTING THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF A FARM SPECIALIZING IN COTTON GROWING

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Abstract. The issue of raising the economic efficiency of agriculture to the optimal level is considered one of the most urgent tasks of the economy of our country today. Because agriculture is one of the main sectors of our country's economy. This issue is currently under the attention of the leadership of our country. Today, the development of scientifically based and practical opinions, proposals and recommendations on further increasing the economic efficiency of existing farms is one of the most urgent issues of today.

Key words. efficiency, economic efficiency, human factor, organizational and economic factors, productivity, farm, management mechanism.

The issue of raising the economic efficiency of agriculture to the optimal level is one of the most urgent tasks of the economy of our country today. Because agriculture is one of the main sectors of our country's economy. This issue is currently under the attention of the leadership of our country. In particular, diversifying agricultural production, improving land and water relations in the field, creating a favorable agribusiness environment and a high added value chain, supporting the development of cooperative relations - "Development of the new Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 strategy" goal 30 is to increase the income of peasants and farmers by at least 2 times through the intensive development of agriculture on a scientific basis, to bring the annual growth of agriculture to at least 5%, and to supply raw materials and production to agro-industrial enterprises in the 141st task increase the volume by 1.5 times, including developing a program for 2022, increasing the volume of industrialized fruits and vegetables to 3.4 million tons, processing capacity to 3.1 million tons, and the level of processing to 16%, processing fruits and vegetables capacity by 3.1 million tons (107 percent), milk by 2.9 million tons (111.5 percent), meat by 410 thousand tons (119 percent) supply, increasing the range of food products (processed meat-milk, fruit-vegetables, oil-oil, etc.) from 898 to 1100, creating 3.2 thousand new jobs, supporting market mechanisms in the sector, in order to widely introduce information and communication technologies, as well as to

effectively use the achievements of science and increase the potential of personnel On October 23, 2019, the adoption of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5853 "On approval of the strategy for the development of agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030" defined the road map of development until 2030. According to the opinion of our economists, A. Zakirov, "Efficiency grows faster than the amount of resources used. Therefore, there is a connection between "Samara" and "Efficiency", which is manifested in the process of development of production. B.T. Salimov, B.B. A group of authors consisting of Berkinov and others "Samara is a broad concept, as a result of any event or activity, it is expressed in the effect of using fertilizers, increasing the yield of crops, increasing the efficiency of fodder, increasing the productivity of livestock. E.J. Yusupov about economic efficiency: "In the conditions of any economic system, two undeniable truths form the basis of the economy. Clarification of these two truths in every way and deep assimilation gives an opportunity to get a full answer to the role and importance of the concept of efficiency in the life of society. Based on this, we will consider the methodological basis of economic efficiency in the example of cotton growing, which is considered the main crop of agriculture. A number of economic indicators are used to determine the economic efficiency of cotton cultivation. There are no clear boundaries in the theoretical interpretation of economic efficiency indicators in cotton farming. Therefore, the issue of determining the ratio of these indicators remains open. It is appropriate to clarify this issue, to choose the most optimal one among the solutions, to be considered as the starting point for studying and evaluating the economic efficiency of cotton farming. Based on the opinions and opinions of scientists who have conducted research on the methodology of economic efficiency evaluation until now, they can be conditionally divided into two groups. Scientists belonging to the first group believe that the criterion indicator of economic efficiency should be the only one. According to them, this indicator has a general characteristic and should objectively and completely reflect the economic efficiency.

The second group of economists advocates that economic efficiency should be determined through a system of indicators. E.J. According to Yusupov, "When comparing the dynamic changes of economic efficiency in the network over the years, it is correct to single out a generalizing indicator from among the indicators. However, the summarizing indicator extracted from the system of indicators must meet the following general requirements, otherwise its use will be pointless and meaningless.

First, it should fully respond to the characteristics of the studied category as much as possible;

Secondly, it embodies the degree of use of land, capital and labor factors involved in obtaining the final result used in the production process;

Thirdly, it should be connected with generalizing indicators used at all levels of management and on the scale of the whole society;

Fourthly, it can be used in practice.

Agriculture is the leading branch of Uzbekistan's agriculture. Currently, cotton is the main source of foreign currency, one of the main sources that ensures the import of food products, medicines, technical and technological equipment, which are vitally important for the Republic. In the process of processing one ton of raw materials, about 3000 m³ of gas, 100-110 kilograms of oil, 2000-250 kilograms of kunjara, 50-60 kilograms of shelukha, 10 kilograms of household soap and other products are produced. . It is necessary to emphasize that in the conditions of transition to market relations, it is necessary to take into account the theoretical and practical interdependence of the factors affecting the economic efficiency of agriculture. For example, in the process of production in agriculture, in the conditions where the influence of the human factor is limited to natural-ecological factors, the violation of any of the agro-technological, organizational-economic, social or legal factors reduces the efficiency of the network. From this point of view, their effective use based on equal treatment of the factors determining the development of the industry and its economic efficiency is important for the development of agriculture and ensuring its economic efficiency.

The economic efficiency of agriculture is largely related to the correct use of land and the increase of productivity on this basis. In this process, the economic efficiency of agriculture is formed depending on the differences and changes within the natural climatic conditions. Because soil fertility, natural climatic conditions, water supply, relief of production areas, distance and proximity of seepage waters and many other conditions affect the economic efficiency of the network. These factors have a unique influence on the process of land use in agriculture, and the possibilities of managing them within the limits of the will of producers are limited. In this regard, it is necessary to adapt the production process to the influence of these factors. Regular improvement of soil fertility in agriculture, on this basis, increase of crop yield, improvement of water supply level of crop areas, placement of new biologically and economically favorable crop varieties for production, improvement of crop yield and crop rotation in the

network means ensuring the compatibility of natural and agro-technological factors through proper implementation. Product growers can use their labor, knowledge and expertise to increase crop productivity by increasing soil fertility. The wider and effective the use of scientific and technical achievements in the agricultural sector, the greater the productivity of the soil, the greater the contribution of living labor spent on it, and the greater the contribution of materialized labor. As a result, the amount of harvest per hectare increases, which ultimately becomes the basis for the development of agriculture.

Organizational and economic factors are of particular importance in the development of agriculture, and are among the factors that tend to be managed by producers in the direction of a certain goal and have a strong influence on the final economic results. In the organization of agriculture, taking into account the demand and supply for the type of product in the countries that produce and consume the product, the existence of issues such as the transformation of farms into the main form of management of the farm in the production of the product, the provision of material and technical resources in the network requires a scientific approach to them. The issues of organizing, managing and increasing economic efficiency of agriculture are in a certain sense related to the laws that are being formed in the producing and consuming countries. Because, not taking into account supply and demand, the main categories that determine the price of the product in the world market, can have a negative effect on the development of the industry. Taking into account the demand and supply for the types of products in the world market, firstly, it allows to clearly determine the cultivated areas necessary for agriculture, and secondly, based on the practice of the countries of the world, the production of products in the agricultural network of our country, domestic provides an opportunity to develop scientifically based ratios that correspond to the state's level of development in terms of consumption and export indicators.

It is important to take into account the unique characteristics of the industry in the organization, management and economic efficiency of agriculture. These features establish some of the features that distinguish agriculture from other sectors. Including:

- that the development of agriculture is a priority direction in meeting the demand of industrial enterprises for raw materials and solving social problems;
- making raw materials grown in agriculture suitable for consumption by members of society requires several stages of processing;

- that producers of products do not have the opportunity to satisfy their consumption requirements of a certain form with intermediate finished products (producers of vegetables, grain, livestock products can use the finished product for personal consumption without any further processing);
- that production in agriculture is a field that requires regular regulation with labor and economic means, etc.

The issues of effective organization of production on farms are directly related to how management is organized. Management activity is one of the diverse aspects of the labor organization process and consists of all the elements characteristic of it - the subject of labor, labor tools, labor and its results. Objective laws of nature, society and thinking form the basis of any goal-oriented activity, including management activity. Management of the enterprise, including management of the actual activities of farms, is a comprehensive activity, and the following elements can be included in its composition:

- management mechanism (general laws, principles, goals and tasks, methods);
- management structure (management bodies, specialist staff, technical means, etc.);
- management process (decision-making and implementation, management technology and procedure, organization of staff activities).

It is known that external and internal factors influence the management of agricultural enterprises, that is, farms.

Internal factors include levers such as the size of the production areas allocated to the farm, the distribution of production resources in the network, the level of technical and technological equipment, methods of labor organization, production costs and price policy. These factors can be planned and controlled to a certain extent.

External factors arise under the influence of the environment outside the agricultural enterprise. Among them, factors such as the actual level of activity of infrastructure entities serving farms, competitive environment in the production process, natural and climatic conditions, political and social factors, legal and regulatory framework and state administration.

Increasing labor productivity is important for network development and economic efficiency. Labor productivity in agriculture is the process of reducing labor costs for the production of a unit of output and is based on:

- financial stability of agricultural holdings;
- the existence of an effective material-technical and services market;
- level of network mechanization;

- product production in accordance with demand and supply;
- less use of live labor, etc.

In the conditions where the laws of market relations apply, the main goal of producers is to get more income, and they choose the most convenient and effective way to achieve their goals. Ultimately, the chosen path creates the formation of labor productivity in different ways. In case of availability of cheap labor in the network, the level of their use is high and justifies the tendency of labor productivity to decrease, and the cheapness of the services of equipment means the tendency of labor productivity to grow in agriculture. So, achieving labor productivity in agriculture is the basis for the formation of the following positive aspects in the network:

- reduction of labor costs, efficient use of land, water, and material resources;
- to achieve an intensive increase in the volume of the product;
- decrease in product cost and increase in income;
- increasing the material interests of producers, etc.

The supply of material and technical resources in agriculture is considered one of the factors that have a strong impact on the development of the industry, and in the conditions of transition to market relations, their purchase prices should be proportional to the purchase prices of the raw materials being produced. On the contrary, the disparity between the prices of the material and technical resources produced in industry and used in agriculture and the purchase prices of raw materials of the product causes the cost of the product to be high, and this situation has a serious negative impact on the economic efficiency of agriculture. can pass the secret. However, the economic efficiency of agriculture depends not only on the prices of material and technical means, but also on their effective use. Failure to carry out agrotechnical activities in a timely manner due to non-effective use of material and technical means causes a decrease in soil fertility and a decrease in crop yield.

Social factors affecting network development are directly related to ownership relations. Adjustment of ownership and use of property in agriculture to the requirements of market relations, in turn, leads to improvement of the relations of producers to property and labor. On this basis, it is necessary to improve the system of material benefits in the formation of agrarian relations in agriculture. This is the main requirement of the market economy based on social relations. The implementation of this goal will depend on the improvement of the legal and regulatory documents in force in the network.

In conclusion, we think that the above-mentioned theoretical foundations are effectively used in the organization and management of agriculture in the farms operating in our country today, in order to increase the agricultural development and economic efficiency of the existing farms to the optimal level. It will be a solid basis for solving problems.

On the basis of the above, the development of scientifically based and practical opinions, proposals and recommendations on further increasing the economic efficiency of existing farms today is considered one of the most urgent issues of today, and the topic chosen on this basis is relevant.

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